

RIPOSTE – Implementation and Testing

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1 Implementation and Testing

This section provides details on the implementation and testing of the developed testbed based on RIPOSTE framework. Section 1.1 describes the implementation of the chosen attack and reconfiguration techniques and Section 1.2 shows a step-by-step guide on how the implementation is tested in regards to functionality and requirements. The implementation (i.e., source code) of the testbed can be found online using the same Zenodo DOI.

1.1 Attack and Response Techniques

The attack used in the simulation is a simple representation of a privilege escalation attack. The car monitors the shadow file (`/etc/shadow`) that stores encrypted passwords of users on the system and can only be read by the root account. Any modification to the attributes of this file requires root privileges and thus, triggering the framework.

For the attack to happen, this simple script is used:

```
1 #!/bin/bash
2
3 sudo chmod +x /etc/shadow
```

That being said, more sophisticated attacks are planned to be used by using vulnerable Raspberry Pi OS's, such as RasPwn OS¹ or DV-PI². Unfortunately, most resources are designed for Raspberry Pi 3 and/or earlier versions and are not compatible with Raspberry Pi 4.

In the remainder of this section we describe the selected response techniques and their implementation when applied in the RIPOSTE testbed.

Graceful Degradation/Limp Mode

This response technique allows the system to continue functioning and prevent a catastrophic failure in the case of a compromise. This is done by lowering the performance of the system or reducing the number of services provided. It is important to mention that every system requires different sets of services to perform its core functionality, and selecting what functionalities/services to disable/enable can widely differ on each system. For this study, the core functionality considered was to keep the operating system running with minimum losses of services. Table 1 shows the services that were available on the systems and Table 2 lists the services that will be disabled in order to limit the privilege escalation attack.

The **SSH** and **bluetooth** services can be used for remote shell access to the system. Thus, disabling them limits the possibility for an attacker to have such access. The **cron** service allows for scheduled jobs to be executed at a certain time. Keeping this enabled can let the attacker schedule an execution of a malicious script allowing him/her to re-enable other services in case they were disabled, and regain access. The **exim4** is a mail transfer agent, and disabling it can limit any private or system information to be sent to the attacker via mail. The **nfs-common** is used to enable the sharing of

¹<http://raspwn.org/>

²<https://whitedome.com.au/re4son/sticky-fingers-dv-pi/>

files between systems that reside within the same local area network. And since an attack can arrive from compromised local systems, malicious scripts can be transferred to the main system.

The following script was used to implement this technique:

```

1  #!/bin/bash
2
3  ARG=$1
4
5  if [ $ARG = "apply" ]
6  then
7      echo "Stopping and disabling SSH"
8      sudo systemctl stop ssh && sudo systemctl disable ssh
9      echo "Stopping and disabling bluetooth"
10     sudo systemctl stop bluetooth && sudo systemctl disable bluetooth
11     echo "Stopping and disabling cron"
12     sudo systemctl stop cron && sudo systemctl disable cron
13     echo "Stopping and disabling exim4"
14     sudo systemctl stop exim4 && sudo systemctl disable exim4
15     echo "Stopping and disabling nfs-common"
16     sudo systemctl stop nfs-common && sudo systemctl disable nfs-common
17 elif [ $ARG = "revert" ]
18 then
19     echo "Starting and enabling SSH"
20     sudo systemctl start ssh && sudo systemctl enable ssh
21     echo "Starting and enabling bluetooth"
22     sudo systemctl start bluetooth && sudo systemctl enable bluetooth
23     echo "Starting and enabling cron"
24     sudo systemctl start cron && sudo systemctl enable cron
25     echo "Starting and enabling exim4"
26     sudo systemctl start exim4 && sudo systemctl enable exim4
27     echo "Starting and enabling nfs-common"
28     sudo systemctl start nfs-common && sudo systemctl enable nfs-common
29 fi

```

Table 1: Available services on the system.

Available services			
alsa-utils	cups-browsed	lvm2	rpebind
anacron	dbus	lvm2-lvmpolld	rsync
apparmor	dhcpcd	mdadm	rsyslog
auditd	dphys-swapfile	mdadm-waitidle	saned
avahi-daemon	exim4	networking	ssh
binfmt-support	haveged	nfs-common	sudo
bluetooth	hddtemp	ntp	triggerhappy
console-setup.sh	hwclock.sh	plymouth	udev
cron	keyboard-setup.sh	plymouth-log	unattended-upgrades
cryptdisks	kmod	procps	uidd
cryptdisks-early	lightdm	raspi-config	x11-common
cups	live-tools	rng-tools	

Reparameterization

Reparameterization is used to dynamically adjust the system based on the situation. The results of applying this technique can lead to a non-optimal state, which is similar to the Graceful Degradation/Limp mode technique. Therefore, the implementation of this technique focuses on making the

Table 2: Services that are disabled in the system.

Disabled services
bluetooth
cron
exim4
nfs-common
ssh

shadow file immutable; preventing any further attribute modifications on this file even by root.

The following script is used to implement this technique:

```
1 #!/bin/bash
2
3 ARG=$1
4
5 if [ $ARG = "apply" ]
6 then
7     sudo chattr +i /etc/shadow
8 elif [ $ARG = "revert" ]
9 then
10    sudo chattr -i /etc/shadow
11 fi
```

Re-instantiation/Restart

This is one of the interesting response techniques that is implemented to better evaluate the framework. The framework should handle the effects of rebooting while successfully assessing the technique. The system that applies this techniques has to save the analysis log before it reboots, finishes rebooting, reconnects back to the server, and then sends the log file with the analysis data.

This response technique also helped in improving the architecture of the framework. If a car loses its connection to the server during the evaluation process for some reason, it can still reconnect and send the analysis log to the server without an issue.

The following script was used to implement this technique:

```
1 #!/bin/bash
2
3 ARG=$1
4
5 if [ $ARG = "apply" ]
6 then
7     sudo reboot
8 elif [ $ARG = "revert" ]
9 then
10    echo "revert"
11 fi
```

1.2 Test Scenarios

Step 1: The server starts to listening on the interface's IP address: 192.168.1.253, with port number: 12321. Figure 1 shows the server in the listening state.

Step 2: Three clients connect to the server by passing in the server's IP address and the port number, sending their technical specifications, and will start the monitoring process, as seen in Figure 2. The server then receives the connection request, sending an acknowledgment message to the client that the connection is successful. The server also receives the technical specifications sent from the

```
pi@raspberrypi:~/Desktop/VehicleCollaboration/Server $ sudo python3 ./server.py
Host: 192.168.1.253
Port: 12321
█
```

Figure 1: Server: listening state.

client, as seen in Figure 3. Furthermore, Figure 3 also shows that there two collaborative clients that connected to the server (WorkshopCar1 and WorkshopCar2) and one non-collaborative client (onRoadCar).

```
pi@raspberrypi:~/Desktop/VehicleCollaboration/onRoadCar $ sudo python3 ./response_component.py
Host: 192.168.1.253
Port: 12321
string message received!
From server: Successfully connected.
Monitoring process is running...
█
```

Figure 2: Client(onRoadCar): successfully connected.

```
New connection at ID 0 ('192.168.1.188', 49084)
init message received!
Software version: 1.0
Hardware specifications: Broadcom BCM2711, Quad core Cortex-A72 (ARM v8) 64-bit SoC @ 1.5GHz
VIN: WorkshopCar2
Collaboration status: True
Busy status: False
New connection at ID 1 ('192.168.1.78', 57884)
init message received!
Software version: 1.0
Hardware specifications: Broadcom BCM2711, Quad core Cortex-A72 (ARM v8) 64-bit SoC @ 1.5GHz
VIN: WorkshopCar1
Collaboration status: True
Busy status: False
New connection at ID 2 ('192.168.1.24', 46436)
init message received!
Software version: 1.0
Hardware specifications: Broadcom BCM2711, Quad core Cortex-A72 (ARM v8) 64-bit SoC @ 1.5GHz
VIN: onRoadCar
Collaboration status: False
Busy status: False
█
```

Figure 3: Server: several clients are connected, listing their technical specifications and their collaboration status.

Step 3: The attack is manually triggered in the onRoadCar in order to start the framework, as seen in the Figure 4.

```
pi@raspberrypi:~ $ sudo chmod +x /etc/shadow
```

Figure 4: Client(onRoadCar): manual execution of the attack script.

By now, the server would manage the collaboration operation with the available workshop cars. After the assessment of all available response techniques, the server lists the results of the evaluation and sends the effective and most efficient response technique to the onRoadCar, as seen in Figure 5.

```
Best effective response technique is reparameterization.
+-----+-----+-----+-----+
| Response Technique Name | Is Effective | Duration | Is Effective And Most Efficient |
+-----+-----+-----+-----+
| limp_mode              | True        | 7.371800661087036 | False |
| reparameterization     | True        | 0.03790020942687988 | True  |
| restart                | False       | 78.56117129325867  | False |
+-----+-----+-----+-----+
Sending final update!
```

Figure 5: Server: listing the results of the evaluation and the best effective response technique.

The onRoadCar receives the update message and applies the response technique suggested by the framework which is reparameterization in this case, as shown in Figure 6.

```
Update received! Applying: reparameterization for: privilege_escalation
Running reparameterization from path data/Response_Techniques/reparameterization
.sh
```

Figure 6: Client(onRoadCar): received the update from the server and applying the suggested response technique.

Step 4: A manual attack is executed again on onRoadCar to check whether the suggested response technique was applied, as shown in Figure 7.

```
pi@raspberrypi:~ $ sudo chmod +x /etc/shadow
chmod: changing permissions of '/etc/shadow': Operation not permitted
```

Figure 7: Client(onRoadCar): checking whether the response technique is applied and working.

Step 5: A manual revert of the reparameterization technique is performed and followed by an execution of the attack. The server returned a response technique suggestion without the need for evaluation of any response technique because all techniques were previously assessed and evaluated, as shown in Figure 8.

```

Evaluation requested by ID: 2 for privilege_escalation. The applied response technique is: reparameterization.
+-----+-----+-----+-----+
| Response Technique Name | Is Effective | Duration | Is Effective And Most Efficient |
+-----+-----+-----+-----+
| limp_mode | True | 7.371800661087036 | False |
| reparameterization | True | 0.03790020942687988 | True |
| restart | False | 78.56117129325867 | False |
+-----+-----+-----+-----+
onRoadCar is already using the most efficient response technique. ACK sent!

```

Figure 8: Server: The onRoadCar requests for evaluation, the server acknowledges that the onRoadCar is using the best response technique.

After the client receives the acknowledgement message, it will execute the response technique it already set up to use, as shown in Figure 9

```

ACK message received from server, running the best response technique.
Running reparameterization from path data/Response_Techniques/reparameterization
.sh

```

Figure 9: Client(onRoadCar): The onRoadCar uses the already applied response technique after receiving an acknowledgement message from the server.